

YUFERING Project

YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH EUROPE-WIDE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

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List of Abbreviations and Definitions

CA	Consortium Agreement
CERI	Community Engaged Research and Innovation
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
EC	European Commission
EEI	European Excellence Initiative
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
EUI	European Universities Initiative
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FOCI	Future-proof Criteria for Innovative European Education
FOREU	Forum of European Universities
FKT	Flipped Knowledge Transfer
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KT	Knowledge Transfer
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KV	Knowledge Valorisation
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
QR	Quick Response
R&I	Research and Innovation
SwafS	Science with and for Society
YUFE	Young Universities for the Future of Europe
WP	Work Package

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REPORT ON DEC ACTIVITIES

1. Section: Introduction

The YUFERING “Report on DEC Activities” is a deliverable produced in order to demonstrate the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) activities to the Research and Innovation (R&I) community, policymakers, and the general public regarding the YUFERING project.

This document is related to Work Package 6 (WP6). The objectives of WP6 are listed below:

- O6.1 Implement and revise as and if needed the proposed dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan.
- O6.2 Design and direct a dissemination plan at all levels of the project implementation.
- O6.3 Raise awareness of the project’s achievements and outcomes within relevant stakeholders, communities, citizens, and organisations who can benefit from the outcomes.
- O6.4 Liaise with other consortia of European Universities and exchange good practices.
- O6.5 Exploit the project results in the optimal manner through open access or commercialisation of Intellectual Property (IP) where applicable and for training in order to attract PhD students and post-doctoral researchers in the YUFERING consortium.

The main purpose of this Deliverable is to report on the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities of the project to the relevant stakeholders and the wider public, including the European Commission (EC). Also, to ensure that both the project impact and practical outcomes were widely disseminated to the appropriate target audiences throughout the project lifecycle (36 months) via appropriate methods.

In order to maximise impact, the chosen transformation modules have a common focus: to widely cooperate with all societal actors and the ecosystem and to transfer knowledge and talent to society. Hence the emphasis in both the R&I agenda and the knowledge transfer (KT) is the community engagement and deployment in society piloting new concepts of community engagement-based R&I and flipped knowledge transfer (FKT) as well as utilizing common infrastructures for R&I activities. Furthermore, to effectively tackle societal challenges, research needs to be more international, collaborative, interdisciplinary and open as well as have the critical mass, hence the Alliance develops new strategies and tools which will enable us to identify, develop and reward talents to increase societal impact across Europe thus creating a genuine single market for knowledge, R&I to circulate in Europe.

YUFERING is also creating a YUFE Open Science Strategy, but it will use Open Science (OS) as an intrinsic mechanism to maximise its own impact, in YUFERING and YUFE sister projects by following all the best practices on Open Access and Open Research Data for H2020 projects, as well as going further (citizen science, research integrity, FAIR data, etc.) since the topic particularly targets OS as one of the main targeted objectives for the specific Science with and for Society (SwafS) call for EU universities.

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To go even further, YUFERING also includes a dedicated task for the collaboration with the other European University Alliances to explore joint structures and sharing best practices for tackling common challenges faced and finding solutions through a European Alliance Forum, initially launched digitally.

2. Section: Definitions and Guidelines

According to the EC, Under Horizon 2020, beneficiaries should engage in dissemination and exploitation activities. As Horizon 2020 is financed by EU citizens, it should benefit the largest number and the fruits of the research reach society as a whole.

Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players, and policymakers. Sharing the research results of the project with the rest of the scientific community fosters the contribution to the progress of science in general. The dissemination of the project outputs is “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.” Whereas exploitation is the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking. Project communication is “a strategically planned process, which starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”. Experience shows it's not always easy to meet these goals.

The differences between Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Differences between Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation¹

¹ Source: European Commission, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation, Why they all matter and what is the difference?

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

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Communication about European research projects should aim to demonstrate the ways in which R&I is contributing to a European “Innovation Union” and account for public spending by providing tangible proof that collaborative research adds value by:

- Showing how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in achieving scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness, and solving societal challenges.
- Showing how the outcomes are relevant to our everyday lives, be creating jobs, introducing novel technologies, or making our lives more comfortable in other ways.
- Making better use of the results, by ensuring they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policymaking and by industry and the scientific community to ensure follow-up.

Regarding specific YUFERING publications, it is ensured that:

- All project beneficiaries agree to the publication.
- The EU and H2020 logos and acknowledgement are included.

Publications indicate the funding by the EC and state that they reflect only the author’s views. In any case, dissemination of results and open access to scientific publications and research data are governed by Article 29 of the GA and Article 8 of the CA.

3. Section: Dissemination Activities

3.1 Exchange of best practices with other European University consortia

The DEC plan of the project suggests creating synergies with other European University Alliances to ensure maximum efficiency and impact of the SwafS action. Topics that lend themselves and will highly benefit from cross-Alliance cooperation include – but are not limited to – legal, regulatory, and financial barriers that may hinder the implementation and systemic impact of the European Universities Initiative (EUI). In this context, challenges and solutions/opportunities identified within YUFERING or other pilots may be applicable to other Alliances as well. Sharing structurally and timely relevant information and recommendations will allow all funded Alliances to prevent duplication of effort and, therefore, allow for a cost-effective investment of the funding. The plan is to have a continuous contact with other EUI Alliances and ensure that through the appropriate networking activities, effective discussion and cooperation can take place towards development of relevant recommendations and joint organisation of communication and dissemination activities.

In April 2023 the European Research Executive Agency published a report that provides an analysis on the intermediate progress in the period of 2021 – 2022 of the 17 European University Alliances projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020 call - Support for the Research and Innovation Dimension of European Universities.

This report supports the implementation of the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda Action 13 “Empower Higher Education Institutions to develop in line with the ERA and in synergy with the European Education Area” and directly contributes to gathering insights for the development of a European Excellence Initiative (EEI) by the EC. The analysis in this report is based on the policy briefs, periodic reports, project deliverables, and reviewer assessments related to YUFE and the other 16 European

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university Alliances² in the first reporting period, covering the first 18 months of their implemented action plans.

Based on the conclusions of the report, the university Alliances have all started exploring joint university structures in their own unique ways to coordinate their activities and facilitate collaboration among the members. Specifically, YUFERING is one of the projects that have conducted a mapping exercise of policies and practices for OS among their members. This allows institutions to identify gaps and benchmark policies and practices and begin tracking progress. Furthermore, YUFERING started to raise awareness of OS among staff and researchers in member institutions. This includes organising workshops³ and developing information materials on OS. This is a first step to help staff and researchers understand OS. As a second step training courses and training materials for researchers and trainers in member institutions were developed. Such activities are crucial for skilling researchers and trainers in how to do OS.

Moreover, YUFERING has developed an OS Calendar 2022 that is aimed at researchers working at member institutions as well as any individuals interested in OS. Each month in the calendar addresses a specific topic for OS and gives links via a Quick Response (QR) code to associated policies, practices, initiatives, events, and video tutorials. The calendar can be used digitally or printed to help researchers more easily learn about OS.

In addition, YUFERING piloted the ambitious and challenging concept of FKT, which requires partners to move out of their comfort zones of the more typical (from the university outwards) formats for Knowledge and Technology Transfer. FKT is characterized by demand driven (from outside in) and solution-oriented involvement of societal and business actors in co-creation that is more interactive and interdisciplinarity. The Alliance has also adopted a mentoring/learning by doing approach where there is some inequity between the partners regarding technology transfer practices. When the EU introduced Knowledge Valorisation (KV) the efforts of YUFERING in FKT shifted towards KV in order to produce outputs that can be easily utilized for implementing the KV guidelines as approved by the EU Council⁴.

YUFERING has not only approached the Citizen and Societal Engagement vertically with a dedicated work package, but also horizontally with Community Engaged Research and Innovation (CERI) agenda setting as a leitmotiv that is embedded in all work packages and drives other transformation modules (such as OS and research infrastructures) across the project. This horizontal approach with one of the transformational modules has the potential to drive significant changes in partner institutions in terms of new approaches to collaboration and in motivating and training academic and non-academic staff to engage with societal actors and thereby strengthen human capital and innovation capacity in the Alliance.

The 17 aforementioned Alliances (including YUFE) from the first EUI pilot call have agreed before submission that they will ensure joint collaboration across their R&I

² The 17 EUI alliances selected by the EC in the first pilot call are: ARQUS, CHARM-EU, CIVICA, CIVIS, ECIU, EDUC, EPICUR, EU-CONEXUS, EU4Art, EUGLOH, EUTOPIA, FORTHEM, 4EU+, SEA-EU, UNA-Europa, UNITE! and YUFE.

³ A full list with the project workshops is presented in Annex 1.

⁴ European Commission, EU valorisation policy: making research results work for society.

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy_en

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project by attending together a Forum of European Universities (FOREU). An Organising Committee composed by 4EU+, CHARM-EU, Circle U, CIVICA, CIVIS, EPICUR, ERUA, EU-CONEXUS, EUTOPIA, FORTHEM and ARQUS, coordinated a Joint SwafS Event in Brussels (Université Libre de Bruxelles, CIVIS) on November 30th and December 1st, 2023 (1.5 days). The event had two objectives: to share good practices and to showcase the great progress made by the Alliances in their R&I dimension. Both objectives were more than achieved. In the event there was participation of members from FOREU1 and FOREU2.

The Joint SwafS Event was carried out to showcase the successful outcomes of research projects from European University Alliances. This was an opportunity to echo the work done by the 41 Alliances and exchange the outcomes with external stakeholders. This was also the chance to discuss as a group with external stakeholders the strategies for the future of research in Europe. During the FOREU event, the YUFE Alliance shared with the other pilots the following outcomes:

- Comprehensive mapping of existing practices, YUFE(RING) practices and progress made/success stories emerged from the implementation of our joint R&I strategy.
- Legal, financial, and regulatory barriers (at local, national and European level) and possible solutions (for YUFE this was the result of the efforts in WP1 Management as well as the horizontal effort from WP2, 3, 4 and 5).

As an outcome of the event⁵, a [poster](#) was produced that highlights 32 Alliances' examples on best practices and outcomes of their R&I projects, organised around the seven transformational modules. All the Alliances' results are linked within the poster and can be accessed at once. In addition, a contact list regarding the R&I dimension of these Alliances is also included.

Beyond the FOREU network, YUFE is in close (bilateral) contact with several Alliances. YUFE, ECIU and EPICUR are still closely connected, working together at various levels, exchanging experiences, and good practices. This connection is facilitated by EPIconnect, an EPICUR platform catering to network-to-network relations, supported by digital collaboration tools. While the initial conversations of the three first generation Alliances has focused on possible collaboration in the form of R&I, the conversations have led to fruitful collaboration in another areas, such as the FOCI (Future-proof Criteria for Innovative European Education) work on the European Degree (Label).

The collaboration between YUFE, ECIU and EPICUR is also continued in the FOCI consortium. The aim of FOCI is to address several all-encompassing challenges, such as the human, technical, data, education, R&I aspects that come with cohesive, cross-border and interdisciplinary education. Its main aim is to work in a common effort on the European Degree (Label), which happened in response to a policy experimentation call launched by the EC under Erasmus+.

While the YUFERING project will be finalized in spring 2024, YUFE is looking into possibilities for continuing the fruitful collaboration of the three Alliances in other projects in future. One direction that YUFE would like to explore is linking the findings on a European Degree (Label) at Bachelor and Master level to the YUFE approach to doctoral and postdoctoral training. This is under development in the YUFE 2030 Erasmus+ and YUFE4Postdoc projects.

⁵ All posters presented in the event can be downloaded [here](#)

Taken together, the different projects run in cooperation between the Alliances in the fields of education and R&I are leading to closer links between the Alliances' missions and allowing our universities to transform and advance in both aspects.

In parallel, bottom-up collaboration on different topics, such as OS, was established among Alliances and upon initiative of the different experts. Such networks have not initially been foreseen in the YUFERING proposal but may find a home in a proposal for a FOR-EU community of practice that will be submitted in response to an Erasmus+ call in February 2024.

3.2 Participation in international conferences, seminars, open events and publications in scientific journals

Although the main focus of YUFERING is not about producing academic R&I output, it resulted in an increased interest and cooperation in the academic YUFE community especially those researchers involved in R&I policy research. Therefore, the outcomes of the project contributed to studies whose results were communicated in international conferences and submitted for publications in international scientific journals of the field. Both processes can be particularly useful since the results of the project will undergo an independent scientific validation test and this is fully line with the envisaged evidence-driven implementation of R&I policies within the EU.

The YUFERING partners coordinated and suggested the most suitable Open Access (OA) outlets for diffusion of the project's results. For journals, the publication process took place initially through the deposit of the papers in the relevant repositories of the YUFERING partners (green OA), as well as the Zenodo repository (an open repository operated by CERN) where the project might have a specific collection of [openly available outputs](#)⁶.

Beyond International Conferences, the work conducted within this project achieved the intended impact on the project's target groups through more specialised and/or local conferences, seminars, and other open events; the relevant list follows:

- EAIR (the European Higher Education Society) 2021, 9–11 September 2021 (Target Groups: Scientific Community, Policymakers), hosted by the Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany
- CHER Conference 2022 (the 34th Annual Conference of the Consortium for Higher Education Researchers), 1–2 September 2022 (Target Group: Scientific Community), hosted by the University of Jyväskylä, Jyväskylä, Finland
- Welcoming Event of the Annual Progress Meeting, 9–10 May 2022 (Target Groups: Open Science Experts, R&I Experts, Rector, and Vice-Rector of Academic Affairs), Nicosia, Cyprus
- STI Conference 2022 (the 26th International Conference on Science, Technology, and Innovation Indicators), 7–9 September 2022 (Target Group: Scientific Community), hosted by the University of Granada, Granada, Spain
- Coordinators' Day European Excellence Initiative, 20 September 2022 (Target Group: Policy Makers)
- Nordic Workshop on Bibliometrics and Research Policy, 21–23 September 2022 (Target Group: Scientific Community), hosted by the University of Turku and Åbo Akademi University, Turku, Finland

⁶ YUFERING on [Zenodo](#)

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- Researchers' Night in Nicosia, Cyprus, 30 September 2022 (Target Groups: School teachers, Researchers, Project Managers, Elementary and Secondary School Children, General Visitors), Nicosia, Cyprus

Figure 2 Researchers' Night in Nicosia

- Researchers' Night in Rijeka, Croatia, 30 September 2022 (Target Groups: School teachers, Researchers, Project Managers, Elementary and Secondary School Children, General Visitors), Rijeka, Croatia

Figure 3 Researchers' Night in Rijeka

- Network of IP Academies (NIPA) in Alicante, Links between YUFERING and the EUIPO, Spain, December 2022 (Target Groups: R&I Professionals, Knowledge Transfer Experts), Alicante, Spain

Figure 4 Network of IP Academies in Alicante

- 2nd TORCH Annual Forum in Dublin, 8 March 2023 (Target Group: Higher Education Community), Dublin, Ireland
- Stakeholder Info Day, 12 May 2023 (Target Groups: R&I Professionals, KT Experts), Nicosia, Cyprus

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Figure 5 Stakeholder Info Day in Nicosia

- The Finish Higher Education Institutions; Quality Network Meeting, 20 June 2023 (Target Group: Higher Education Community), Kuopio, Finland
- XV Symposium of the Consortium of Higher Education Researchers, 15-16 August 2023 (Target Group: Scientific Community), Jyväskylä, Finland
- Research Service Days 2023, 21-23 August 2023 (Target Group: Higher education community), Espoo, Finland
- KOTA Seminar, 28 August 2023 (Target Groups: Policymakers, Higher Education Community), Tampere, Finland
- 35th Annual Conference of the Consortium for Higher Education Researchers (CHER Conference), 30 August-1 September 2023 (Target Group: Scientific Community), Vienna, Austria
- II European Alliances Forum, 14 September 2023, Barcelona, Spain
- Open Science Bottom-Up Implementation in the YUFERING Project Seminar, 15 September 2023 (Target Groups: Open Science Experts, R&I Experts, PhD students, Researchers, Librarians), Online
- 27th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators (STI 2023) Poster Presentation, 28 September 2023 (Target Group: Scientific Community), Leiden, the Netherlands
- Nordic Workshop on Bibliometrics and Research Policy (NWB 2023) Poster Presentation, 11-13 October 2023 (Target Group: Scientific Community), Gothenburg, Sweden
- Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023⁷, 30 November-1 December 2023 (Target Groups: Representatives of the FOREU Alliances, EC Officials, External Stakeholders), hosted by Université Libre de Bruxelles, Brussels, Belgium

The team involved in Task 4.3 disseminated more widely to the public with two non-refereed publications and one refereed publication, as follows:

Pietilä, M., Kekäle, J. & Rintamäki, J. 2022. [Tutkimuksen arviointi muutoksessa](#). Tieteessä tapahtuu, 4/2022, 41–44.

Rintamäki, K. & Pietilä, M. 2022. [Tutkimuksen tuki yhdistää kirjastoja Euroopan reunalta toiselle](#). Signum, 55(4), 33–36.

Pietilä, M. From an input to an output: the discursive uses of external research funding in academic career assessments⁸. Higher Education Policy, 2024.

All YUFERING-related peer-reviewed papers followed the mandatory regulations for Horizon 2020 projects (art. 29.2 of the GA).

⁷ [Mapping the Alliances R&I Best Practices around the SwafS Transformation Modules](#)

⁸ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/s41307-023-00339-8>

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Finally, the YUFERING project has played a pivotal role in supporting the University of Cyprus to design and execute a series of lectures for Free Universities⁹ in collaboration with local Municipalities, communities, and various societal entities. Recognising the significance of lifelong learning, this initiative aims to promote knowledge and foster the spirit of dialectical thinking. The University of Cyprus, through the YUFERING project, has organised a diverse range of public events and lectures. These aim to illustrate the value of education, culture, and science, while emphasising the engagement of citizens with the primary public institution in Cyprus. The YUFERING project, in conjunction with the University of Cyprus, stands as a testament to the collective effort to create an environment that values and supports education, knowledge, and cultural enrichment.

3.3 Policy Recommendation Reports

All policy recommendation reports produced through the project are openly available (OA) for all users and were particularly disseminated to the relevant policymakers, both at the EU level and at the national level of the YUFERING partners. It is of utmost importance to obtain the endorsement of EU and national R&I structures, since without this support the foreseen transformations will not be materialised and legal, regulatory, and financial barriers will not be surmounted. The YUFE Alliance also published all relevant policy notes on the relevant portal of the YUFE Virtual Campus. All policy communications were also be shared with the EC via the relevant project officer assigned by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD).

Beyond the legal, regulatory, and financial barriers identified and the foreseen transformations, specialised Policy Briefs focused on outputs from the transformational areas of the project are foreseen (e.g., work being done on the development of a common profile and career development path for KT professionals).

Two (2) ERA Policy Briefs were submitted as individual deliverables of WP1 i.e., D1.5 Policy Brief 1 (UCY, M18) and D1.6 Policy Brief 2 (UCY, M36). In both policy briefs, the European University pilot Alliances reported on the progress made through cooperation in selected R&I areas and provided recommendations to the EC for further policy development. The policy briefs are relevant not only to the communities of the YUFE Alliance but also to the wider public, and therefore instead of the YUFE Virtual Campus the consortium uses the [project webpage](#) and [Zenodo](#).

Apart from the aforementioned policy briefs, Taks 5.1 Open Science Practice and Policy Commons for YUFE Partners delivered among others the deliverable D5.1 Report: Towards a YUFE Open Science Commons (UC3M, M36), also open to the public. The specific deliverable is a final report/proposal of a common YUFE Open Science Policy and Roadmap based on the previous mutual learning exercises among the members.

3.4 Knowledge exploitation and educational material

The project produced several R&I policy outputs and educational material, which generated intellectual property worth exploiting further. As the primary aim of the project is to create valuable input for the YUFERING partners enabling them to align their R&I policies and priorities to the optimal extent, most results were fully accessible to all types of users. However, several education and training materials were created for researchers, students, policymakers, and citizens. Some of this material was in the

⁹ <https://www.ucy.ac.cy/events/free-universities/?lang=en>

form of online modules and courses. This type of intellectual property was not exploited commercially but was made available - free of charge - on demand for policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders for the duration of the project and after its completion. YUFERING training materials were, as much as possible, delivered as OER (Open Educational Resources) and developed during the activities of the YUFERING WPs.

3.5 Intellectual Property Management

The legal framework of the Consortium and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues were represented by the GA of the Partners with the EC, implemented by the Consortium Agreement (CA) that was signed before the end of the finalisation procedure of the grant agreement (GA) with the EC in case of approval of the proposal. A CA was prepared in order to regulate the arising knowledge-related and proprietary issues. The CA essentially contains the following points:

- The internal organisation of the Consortium, its governance structure, decision-making processes, and management arrangements.
- Arrangements for the distribution of the contribution among partners and among activities.
- Provisions for the settlement of disputes within the partnership.
- Specific arrangements concerning IPR to be applied among the partners and their affiliates, in compliance with the general arrangements stipulated in the contract.
- Explicit provision for background and foreground IP and the rights of each partner for their use both within and after the project.
- Any other provisions necessary to ensure a sound management of the project.

The final aim of the document is that of giving the power of governing the Consortium to the Coordinator in respect to the GA signed with the EC.

3.6 FAIR Data Management

The project generated several surveys, reports, action plans, guidelines, manuals, and pilots. Most of these outputs - where allowed by their nature - are openly accessible to the public, following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, when privacy or other legal issues are shorted out. There is increased caution to respect personal data especially when these are received from the public either in the frame of the on-line public dialogue or in the frame of citizen-engagement in connection with the transformation modules of the proposal. All data collected were hosted in a trusted FAIR data repository agreed by all partners. The curation and preservation of the collected data were carried out by the High-Performance Computing (HPC) facility personnel of the University of Cyprus, in consultation with the YUFERING Coordinators and the YUFE Management, both during and after the completion of YUFERING. All data management activities were handled based on the Data Management Plan produced within the frame of Task 1.4 in WP1.

4. Section: Communication Activities

Several communication activities took place throughout the duration of YUFERING, all in line with the communication strategy of the YUFE Alliance in order to secure coherence of approaches in the messages that are transmitted to the public regarding the education, research and innovation dimensions of our EUI. The YUFERING communication measures targeted the maximum outreach of the project activities and

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results, mostly to the public and the societal stakeholders as the scientific community were regularly informed via the dissemination activities mentioned above.

4.1 Communication Toolkit

Throughout the lifetime of the project, several communication activities took place aiming at making the purpose of the project known to academics, policy makers, innovators, and citizens. These were:

- The creation of the project image including the logo (stemming from the main YUFE logo) and the fact sheet.

Figure 6 YUFERING Logo

The fact sheet was developed as a general information tool for the project. It is the “identity card” of the project, highlighting the project’s background, main objectives and impact.

Figure 7 YUFERING Fact Sheet

- The YUFERING Newsletter communicated timely and valuable project information about several aspects of the project such as upcoming events,

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workshops, opportunities for engagement, project’s highlights. In total five (5) Newsletters were sent throughout the project’s duration and are presented in Annex 2.

4.2 Media Corner

The dedicated YUFERING project webpage is the project’s main gateway to the outside world, providing information on the project objectives, partners, results, impact, news, and events. The webpage is available at <https://yufe.eu/yufering/>.

The webpage is attractive, simple, easy to navigate and mobile friendly. The webpage manager (YUFE) is responsible for the updating process, as well as the content management system. The webpage also includes links to dedicated pages on social media.

Figure 8 the YUFERING presents page visits records, offering insights into user engagement on the website. Additionally, a comprehensive analysis spanning from January 2022 to August 2023 is included.

Figure 8 YUFERING Web Page Analytics (Jan 2022 - Aug 2023)

4.3 Communication Channels

The use of social media is important in order to raise awareness on the work undertakes by the project. By using social media the project aims to fulfill the following objectives:

- Maximise the return on investment by steering traffic to the YUFERING webpage;
- Complement traditional communication channels, e.g. printed publications, events, press outreach etc.;
- Provide a low-barrier method for audiences to interact;
- Monitor mentions of the YUFERING partners, project outcomes and other important activities;
- Provide on-site coverage of key events for those who cannot attend.

The YUFERING project used the communication channels of the YUFE project, managed by the YUFE Communication team. The following table provides details on the social media channels and the relevant accounts.

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Table 1 YUFERING Communication Channels

	E-mail	yufering@ucy.ac.cy	
	Facebook	@YUFE Alliance	https://www.facebook.com/YUFEalliance/
	Twitter	@AllianceYufe	https://twitter.com/allianceyufe
	Linkedin	@YUFE Alliance	https://www.linkedin.com/company/young-universities-for-the-future-of-europe/
	Instagram	yufe_alliance	https://www.instagram.com/yufe_alliance/
	Youtube	YUFE Alliance	https://www.youtube.com/@yufealliance5305
	Newsletter	YUGERING Newsletter	

The following tables delve into critical aspects of the online performance, highlighting key metrics, trends, and noteworthy observations. It is important to note, however, that the website data is currently impacted by a synchronisation issue between Google Analytics, resulting in partial extracts rather than a complete representation.

The YUFERING social media status is also summarised. It is essential to acknowledge the limitations imposed by recent changes in X (former Twitter), affecting our access to X insights compared to our previous capabilities. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) may exhibit slight variations across platforms due to differences in reporting formats.

Figure 9 YUFERING Social Media Analytics¹⁰

Facebook						
Facebook followers by gender and age			Facebook followers by top cities		Facebook followers by top countries	
Age	Women	Men	Top cities	Value	Top countries	Value
18-24	9.5%	5.0%	Torun, Pologne	5.2%	Chypre	11.8%
25-34	23.2%	17.3%	Maastricht, Pays-Bas	4.0%	Pologne	11.3%
35-44	14.6%	9.0%	Rijeka, Croatie	3.9%	Belgique	9.1%
45-54	8.5%	4.0%	Nicosie	3.5%	Pays-Bas	8.8%
55-64	3.6%	2.2%	Rome, Latium, Italie	3.2%	Croatie	8.7%
65+	1.4%	1.7%	Anvers, Belgique	2.7%	Italie	8.3%
Facebook followers			Brême, Allemagne	1.9%	Allemagne	6.1%
FB_PAGE,FOLLOW,UNIQUE_USERS			Zagreb, Croatie	1.7%	Espagne	4.3%
2374 Followers			Madrid, Espagne	1.6%	Finlande	3.0%
Source: January 7th, 2021 - February 7th, 2024			Strovolos, Chypre	1.6%	Royaume-Uni	2.4%
		11/21-12/22	01/23-02/24			
Facebook Reach		50,168	28,971	42.30%		
Facebook Profile Visits		4,991	8,361	67.40%		
Facebook Page New Likes		250	149	27.70%		

¹⁰ Facebook Reach: This metric counts reach from the organic or paid distribution of your Facebook content, including posts, stories and ads. It also includes reach from other sources, such as tags, check-ins and Page or profile visits. This number also includes reach from posts and stories that were boosted. Reach is only counted once if it occurs from both organic and paid distribution.

Facebook Profile Visits: The number of times your Page or profile was visited.

Facebook Page New Likes: The number of follows in the selected time period.

Instagram Reach: This metric counts reach from the organic or paid distribution of your Instagram content, including posts and stories that were boosted. Reach is only counted once if it occurs from both organic and paid distribution.

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Instagram

Instagram followers by gender and age			Instagram followers by top cities		Instagram followers by top countries	
Age	Women	Men	Top cities	Value	Top countries	Value
18-24	20.2%	11.1%	Maastricht, Pays-Bas	8.0%	Allemagne	13.5%
25-34	27.4%	16.2%	Brême, Allemagne	7.4%	Pays-Bas	13.0%
35-44	10.4%	5.1%	Anvers, Belgique	5.4%	Belgique	11.8%
45-54	3.7%	0.9%	Rome, Latium, Italie	5.1%	Italie	9.1%
55-64	2.6%	1.5%	Madrid, Espagne	2.7%	Espagne	8.5%
65+	0.7%	0.2%				

Instagram followers	11/21-12/22	01/23-02/24
IG_ACCOUNT,FOLLOW,UNIQUE_USERS		
1420 Followers	Instagram Reach 4,795	5,510 14.90%
Source: January 7th, 2021 - February 7th,2024	Instagram Profile Visits 3,850	4,521 17.10%
	New Instagram Followers	373

LinkedIn

Visitor demographics			Audience Location by top cities	
Sector	Followers	%	Location	Total followers
Education 988 (16.1%)	988	16.1	Maastricht, Netherlands	261
Research 475 (7.7%)	475	7.7	Antwerp Metropolitan Area, Belgium	217
Business Development 474 (7.7%)	474	7.7	Greater Madrid Metropolitan Area, Spain	196
Community and Social Services 354 (5.8%)	354	5.8	Brussels Metropolitan Area, Belgium	178
Program and Project Management 351 (5.7%)	351	5.7	Greater Paris Metropolitan Region, France	112
Media and Communication 308 (5%)	308	5.0	The Randstad, Netherlands, Netherlands	93
Operations 274 (4.5%)	274	4.5	Greater Bremen Area, Germany	92
Administrative 216 (3.5%)	216	3.5	Greater Rome Metropolitan Area, Italy	90
Marketing 143 (2.3%)	143	2.3	London Area, United Kingdom, United Kingdom	71
Engineering 102 (1.7%)	102	1.7	Greater Rijeka Area, Croatia	64
			Nicosia, Cyprus	55
			Torun Metropolitan Area, Poland	51
			Greater Barcelona Metropolitan Area, Spain	36
			Helsinki Metropolitan Area, Finland	36
			More...	

LinkedIn Followers
Source: February 6th, 2023 - February 7th, 2024
1186 New Followers (February 6th, 2023 - February 7th, 2024)
3417 Followers

LinkedIn

Competitors Analysis (Alliances)					
Page	Total Followers	New Followers	Total post engagements	Total posts	
CHARM-EU	2260	1019	5458	196	
EPICUR University Alliance	1922	517	955	76	
4EU+ Alliance	3299	1514	3237	148	
Arqus European University Alliance	2531	1051	3266	317	
Una Europa	5916	2146	7596	234	
ECIU	3260	1076	5500	135	
EU-CONEXUS	2519	900	4722	228	
EUTOPIA	4165	1811	3657	237	
YUFE Alliance	3417	1186	2392	128	

Highlights	
Data for 2/6/2023 - 2/5/2024	
Reactions	2.021
Comments	17
Reposts	347

Twitter

28 day summary with change over previous period	
Post impressions	1.702 75.8%
Followers	2.107

4.4 Public dialogue on-line distributed platform

YUFERING implemented an interpersonal (two-way) communication platform on the YUFE Virtual Campus, as well as across available on-line scientific and social networks. This fostered awareness and allowed the YUFE Alliance to receive feedback on YUFERING activities and measures from the scientific community, the public,

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policymakers, and all other interested parties. The project webpage that was developed on the YUFE website/Virtual Campus hosted information on YUFERING partners and activities. Relevant information was also posted on websites and media channels of scientific networks such as Academia, Research Gate and social media such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and others.

Since dissemination, exploitation and communication activities tend to have a significant overlap, all envisaged activities are listed below in order to provide a clear view of the DEC plan of the project and the metrics for the realisation of each activity.

- Existing opportunities for interested audiences, such as the European Researcher's Night which is organised annually every last Friday of September in all EU member states, were leveraged to promote YUFERING and R&I policy more broadly and were already mentioned in section 3.2.
- Press releases were submitted to local and international media regarding key project milestones and highlighting the role of the consortium partners and are included in Table 2.

Furthermore, although developed initially as a deliverable on OS, the YUFERING calendar has been a significant success, not only as a deliverable but also as a dissemination tool. The YUFE Alliance members shared it with their network via different means and social media. The nature of the Calendar as openly accessible and customisable, has led to its adoption by other academics or professionals who then customised and shared the calendar through their social media and networks, increasing public awareness of this project and leading to conversations on OS. Therefore, the YUFERING calendar was utilised by project partners as a dissemination material as well.

Table 2 Social Media, Website and Other Online Dissemination Activities

Social Media, Webpage and Other Online Dissemination Activities						
Code	Short Description	Link (if available)	Channel	Date Published	Disseminator	Target groups reached
O-1	YUFERING Open Science Calendar	https://twitter.com/OpenUC3M/status/1485986509786423311 https://twitter.com/evamen/status/1487021879424655360	Twitter	25/01/2022	UC3M	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
O-2	Announcement of the new project YUFERING	https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/news/yufe-receive-%E2%82%AC2-million-research-and-innovation	Website UM	17/08/2020	UM	General Public
O-3	News Release on YUFE Webpage	https://yufe.eu/yufe/yufe-alliance-further-expands-its-vision-for-the-development-of-a-true-european-university-through-research-and-innovation/	Website YUFE	N/A	YUFE	General Public
O-4	Post about upcoming YUFERING project	https://www.facebook.com/YUFEalliance/photos/curious-to-find-out-more-about-our-new-horizon-2020-funded-yufering-project-find/777086159704432/	Facebook	30/07/2020	YUFE	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
O-5	Local press release about the new project YUFERING	https://www.music.net.cy/to-panepistimio-kyproy-syntonizei-to-neo-chrimatodotoymenou-ergo-yufering/	Press	01/08/2020	UCY	General Public
O-6	Post about the 2022 Annual Progress Meeting	https://twitter.com/SZelenika/status/1523968016765104131	Twitter	10/05/2022	UNIRI	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
O-7	News Release on UNIRI Webpage	https://uniri.hr/en/vijesti/researchers-across-yufe-alliance-asked-to-be-part-of-research-and-innovation-survey/	Website UNIRI	05/10/2021	UNIRI	General Public

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Social Media, Webpage and Other Online Dissemination Activities						
Code	Short Description	Link (if available)	Channel	Date Published	Disseminator	Target groups reached
O-8	Press release on UCY Webpage for YUFERING Annual Progress Meeting 2022	https://websites.ucy.ac.cy/pr/documents/Press_Releases/2022/ENGLISH_PRESS_2022/YUFERING.pdf	Website UCY	19/05/2022	UCY	General Public
O-9	Press release on local news	https://paideia-news.com/panepistimio-kyproy/2022/05/19/synantisi-toy-ergoy-yufering-tis-symmaxias-nearon-panepistimion-gia-to-mellon-tis-eyropis-sto-pan/	Press	19/05/2022	UCY	General Public
O-10	YUFERING Calendar in the GUNI Report	https://www.guni-call4action.org/article/open-science-observations-universities-agents-paradigm-change	Report	22/05/2022	GUNI	Academics Policymakers Staff
O-11	YUFE and YUFERING presentation on Charm EU Webpage	https://www.charm-eu.eu/sites/default/files/2022-03/20220302%20Presentation%20TORCH%20event%20YUFERING%20WP2%20final.pdf	Website Charm EU	02/03/2022	N/A	Academics Policymakers Students Researchers Staff
O-12	Post on UCY facebook page about the YUFERING Annual Progress Meeting	https://www.facebook.com/UniversityOfCyprus/photos/a.364088717008419/5090231527727424/?type=3	Facebook	26/05/2022	UCY	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
O-13	Post on UCY LinkedIn page about the YUFERING Annual Progress Meeting	https://cy.linkedin.com/posts/university-of-cyprus_yufering-horizon2020-activity-6935511878936760320-uKqX?trk=public_profile_like_view	LinkedIn	01/05/2022	UCY	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
O-14	News Release on YUFE Webpage about the WP2 workshop offered in June 2022	https://yufe.eu/yufering/community-engaged-research-the-involvement-of-academic-and-governmental-actors-in-climate-related-flood-risks/	Webpage YUFE	01/06/2022	YUFE	Academics PhD students Staff General Public

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Social Media, Webpage and Other Online Dissemination Activities						
Code	Short Description	Link (if available)	Channel	Date Published	Disseminator	Target groups reached
O-15	Post on YUFE Twitter about the WP2 workshop in June 2022	https://twitter.com/allianceyufe/status/1531934202563907585	Twitter	01/06/2022	YUFE	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
O-16	Dissemination of Evaluation Criteria at the Open Science Conference of Science Europe	N/A	Other	18/10/2022		Academics Policymakers Students Researchers Staff
O-17	News Item on YUFERING Webpage	https://yufe.eu/yufe/lets-talk-about-research-innovation-and-the-power-of-science/	Webpage YUFERING	29/10/2022	YUFE	Academics PhD students Staff General Public
O-23	WP2 Workshop How to start a business from scratch?	https://www.instagram.com/p/CtMCkYyosYS/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igshid=MzRiODBiNWFiZA%3D%3D https://www.facebook.com/YUFEalliance/posts/pfbid02o4BvhFgEkbvvcvVJvmZXgrUrfWudnKb5Gup4J71xZ9RnePJnCunRnchfLjH1LqMEI?mibextid=YxdKMJ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072183039123947520?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	Instagram Facebook Linkedin	26/06/2023	YUFE UM	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
O-24	Open Science bottom-up implementation in the YUFERING project	https://eventos.uc3m.es/101805.html	Webpage UC3M	N/A	UC3M	Academics PhD students Staff General Public

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Social Media, Webpage and Other Online Dissemination Activities						
Code	Short Description	Link (if available)	Channel	Date Published	Disseminator	Target groups reached
O-25	Subscribe to the Newsletter	https://forms.office.com/pages/responsepage.aspx?id=tObRjayNjkCNjWdT6YAFMKI2dqOKt7hHsl9Am5dXhNxURFZVQ0s5NUJMUUo3MkhYNIBIMEIWWdg2QS4u	Webpage YUFERING Social Media Channels	26/09/2023	YUFE	Academics Students Staff Researchers
O-26	WP2 Workshop on Valorization	https://www.instagram.com/p/CuoUtZoIQIq/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igshid=MzRIODBiNWFIZA== https://www.linkedin.com/posts/young-universities-for-the-future-of-europe_yufering-workshop-research-activity-7085165987691470848-gGDK/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=763157712478695&set=a.511256794335456&mibextid=zDhOQc	Instagram Linkedin Facebook	07/09/2023	YUFE UM	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
		https://yufe.eu/yufering/workshop-research-valorization/	Webpage YUFERING	12/07/2023		
O-27	WP2 Workshop on Circular Economy	https://www.facebook.com/YUFEalliance/posts/pfbid02eeZnULnXauXMQGySFck27BknnzvdhaUZYZwL6wLWk8y3SefGQZz8RKgh48paDPXLI?mibextid=YxdKMJ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/young-universities-for-the-future-of-europe_circulareconomy-sustainability-workshop-activity-7119979151935029248--nDu?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	Facebook Linkedin	06/11/2023	YUFE UM	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media

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Social Media, Webpage and Other Online Dissemination Activities						
Code	Short Description	Link (if available)	Channel	Date Published	Disseminator	Target groups reached
		https://yufe.eu/yufe/empowering-the-community-through-circular-economy-research-shaping-a-sustainable-future-together/	Webpage YUFERING	06/11/2023		Academics PhD students Staff General Public
O-28	WP2 Community engaged research and innovation (CERI) & Participatory Research Architecture: Values and Key Principles AND Boosting community engaged research and innovation (CERI) & Participatory Research Trustworthiness	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=834597545334711&set=pb.100063534194848.-2207520000 https://www.linkedin.com/posts/young-universities-for-the-future-of-europe_researchandinnovation-communityengagement-activity-7125060998574559233-NkJU?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop https://www.instagram.com/p/CzObtZkl6mE/ https://twitter.com/AllianceYufe/status/1719276120124620901	Facebook Linkedin Instagram Twitter	17/10/2023 31/10/2023	YUFE UM	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
		https://yufe.eu/yufering/community-engaged-research-and-innovation-workshops/ https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/events/ceri-articipatory-research-workshops-12	Webpage YUFERING Webpage UM	31/10/2023		
O-29	WP4 Online Language Workshop	https://yufe.eu/yufering/online-language-workshop-revise-review-rewrite-how-to-edit-your-academic-texts-as-a-non-native-speaker/	Webpage YUFERING	23/11/2023	YUFE	Academics PhD students Staff General Public

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Social Media, Webpage and Other Online Dissemination Activities						
Code	Short Description	Link (if available)	Channel	Date Published	Disseminator	Target groups reached
O-30	WP2 Entrepreneurial Edge Workshop: Ignite Your Competence using the EntreComp Framework	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=856918663102599&set=pb.100063534194848.-2207520000.%20%20%20%20%20%20%20%20%20%20https%3A%2F%2Fwww.linkedin.com%2Fposts%2Fyoung-universities-for-the-future-of-europe_researchandinnovation-communityengagement-activity-7125060998574559233-NkJU%3Futm_source%3Dshare.https://www.linkedin.com/posts/young-universities-for-the-future-of-europe_entrecomp-innovationleadership-professionaldevelopment-activity-7135258159941611521-Qt07?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop.https://www.instagram.com/p/C0gcZqhodlO/.https://twitter.com/AllianceYufe/status/1729495974916018562	Facebook Linkedin Instagram Twitter	06/12/2023	YUFE UM	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media
		https://yufe.eu/yufering/entrepreneurial-edge-workshop-ignite-your-competence-using-the-entrecomp-framework/	Webpage YUFERING			Academics PhD students Staff General Public

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Social Media, Webpage and Other Online Dissemination Activities						
Code	Short Description	Link (if available)	Channel	Date Published	Disseminator	Target groups reached
O-34	WP2 Structural Adjustment for 21st Century Resilience: Transforming the Democratic Republic of Congo Economy	https://yufe.eu/yufering/workshop-on-structural-adjustment-for-21st-century-resilience-transforming-the-drc-economy/ https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/events/workshop-structural-adjustment-21st-century-resilience-transforming-drc-economy https://www.linkedin.com/events/workshop-communityengagedresea7160212753394126849/comments/ https://m.facebook.com/YUFEalliance/posts/495622931184091/	Webpage YUFERING UM Website Linkedin Facebook	19/12/2023	YUFE UM	Everyone who follows YUFE on social media Researchers Reseach Assistants Students
O-35	YUFERING Newsletters	N/A	N/A	25/09/2023	YUFERING	Academics Students Staff Researchers
				25/10/2023		
				05/12/2023		
				09/01/2024		
				01/02/2024		

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5. Section: Key Performance Indicators

The performance of the DEC was monitored throughout the project with specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and more targeted activities were taking place when/if needed.

Upon the completion of the project the targeted values suggested in the GA were reached.

Table 3 R&I Key Performance Indicators

Area	Description	Upon Project Completion	
		GA	Actual
R&I Transformation KPIs	New R&I Policies introduced	3	3
	R&I-specific Action Plans formulated and implemented	5	5
	Personnel members of YUFE partners engaged in knowledge exchange activities	≥150	~ 200
	Open Access R&I material shared amongst YUFE partners	100	~ 100
	Pilots or test beds/cases	>10	12
R&I Social Impact KPIs	# of engagement partnerships analysed by topic or geographic area of community activity	>50	~ 60
	% of YUFE alliance researchers participating in engaged research	2	~ 20
	% of YUFE alliance researchers participating in flipped knowledge transfer	1	~ 10
	Publications and other outputs arising from engaged partnership (academic and non-academic)	5	26
	Community and citizens rating of partnership experiences and reported benefits and impacts	7/10	8.8/10
R&I Funding KPIs	R&I expenditure from YUFE partners (in-kind & cash, internal & external)	> €1million	>€16million
	Submitted joint YUFE R&I Proposals	10	10
	Successful joint YUFE R&I Proposals	>2	7
R&I Human Capital KPIs	New doctorate candidates	10	~ 15
	Post-docs seconded in 2 or more YUFE partners	10	~ 15
	Shared R&I Staff Development Offers	5	~ 20
	Expert Networks created	5	5
Policy & Societal Impact KPIs	ERA priorities addressed	4	5
	UN Sustainable Development Goals addressed	5	5
	Policy recommendations reports	3	3

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Table 4 DEC Key Performance Indicators

Area	Description	Metric	Upon Project Completion
Public & Societal Awareness	Active interactions of YUFE profile or partners institutional/individual profiles in Social Networks	# of visits/ followers	Facebook: 2374
			Instagram: 1420
			LinkedIn: 3417
			Twitter: 2107
Public & Societal Awareness	Website	# of visits/ responses	>1466
	Events for the community/wider public attended/organised	# of events/ attendees	8
	Media Coverage/Press Releases	# of media articles	3
Scientific Networking (academic and non-academic)	Organisation of lectures/ colloquia/ seminars/ workshops	# of attendees	> 300
	Newsletter of the project	# of recipients	140
	New scientific collaborations established	New MoUs and/or partnership in proposals or papers	12
Engagement of policymakers, community & societal stakeholders	Meetings with policymakers	# of meetings	10
	Meetings with societal stakeholders	# of meetings	10
	Publications and other outputs from community engaged partnerships	# of publications/ other outputs	26
	Policy reports produced	# of reports	3
Education/ Training	Online modules/ online presentations produced	# of modules or educational resources	21
	Community/ Citizens, policymakers, researchers trained	# of attendees	>1000

6. Section: Conclusions

In conclusion, the "Report on DEC Activities" within the YUFERING project serves as a comprehensive overview of the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities conducted under WP6 in horizontal connection with WPs 2-5. This deliverable outlines the ways through which the strategic objectives of the project were disseminated and communicated, emphasising the importance of community engagement, KT, and OS to maximise societal impact and address European challenges collaboratively.

The YUFERING project demonstrates a commitment to enhancing collaboration among European University Alliances, exemplified by its active participation in the FOREU and the Joint SwafS Event. The analysis of intermediate progress, as presented in the European Research Executive Agency's report, showcases YUFERING's dedication to mapping policies, fostering awareness of OS, and promoting joint structures for tackling common challenges across the consortium.

The project's dedication to OS is evident through the development of an OS Strategy, including an OS Calendar, and the appropriate means to guide researchers towards

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the implementation of Full Open Science practices. YUFERING's horizontal approach, integrating CERI throughout its WPs, demonstrates a commitment to driving significant changes in partner institutions by fostering collaboration, innovation, and human capital development.

YUFERING's active involvement in international conferences, seminars, and open events reflects its commitment to sharing research outcomes and engaging with various stakeholders. The project's contributions to conferences such as the SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 exemplify its dedication to showcasing progress and exchanging ideas with external stakeholders.

Furthermore, YUFERING's efforts in policy recommendation reports, ERA Policy Briefs, and open dissemination of educational materials highlight its commitment to influencing R&I policies at both EU and national levels. The project's engagement with the broader academic community and the public is evident through its participation in Researchers' Nights and various conferences, fostering knowledge dissemination and community engagement.

The careful management of intellectual property and adherence to FAIR data principles ensure transparent governance and protection of rights among project partners. YUFERING's commitment to ethical data management and its use of a trusted FAIR data repository underscore the project's dedication to responsible and transparent research practices. These issues alongside all other IP related matters were regulated by the commonly designed and agreed Consortium Agreement of the consortium.

The communication activities undertaken by YUFERING have played a pivotal role in disseminating information, engaging stakeholders, and enhancing public awareness of the project's objectives and outcomes. The implementation of a well-crafted Communication Toolkit, including a distinctive logo and a comprehensive fact sheet, has served as an effective identity card for the project, facilitating clear communication of its background, main objectives, and impact.

The YUFERING Newsletter, comprising five editions throughout the project's duration, has been a valuable tool for timely communication, providing updates on events, workshops, opportunities for engagement, and project highlights. This regular communication has not only informed the scientific community but also engaged policymakers, innovators, and citizens, aligning with the project's commitment to broad societal impact.

The project's Media Corner, represented by its dedicated webpage, served as a central hub for information dissemination. The webpage, characterised by its attractive design, simplicity, and mobile-friendly interface, ensured accessibility and ease of navigation. The integration of web analytics further reflects the project's commitment to understanding and optimising its online presence.

Utilising various communication channels, including social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube, has enabled YUFERING to reach diverse audiences and maximise the impact of its communication efforts. By leveraging the existing communication channels of the YUFE project, YUFERING has successfully complemented traditional communication methods, monitored project mentions, and provided real-time coverage of key events.

The implementation of a public dialogue on the YUFE Virtual Campus and across online scientific and social networks has facilitated two-way communication, allowing the YUFE Alliance to receive feedback from a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including the scientific community, policymakers, and the public. This open platform has enhanced awareness and engagement with YUFERING activities.

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In summary, the robust DEC Plan implemented by YUFERING has not only ensured coherence in messaging but has also effectively reached and engaged diverse audiences, contributing to the project's overall success in disseminating information and fostering meaningful dialogue within the broader community.

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4. Communication and Dissemination in Horizon 2020, European Commission Directorate – General for Research and Innovation, 2017.
5. Horizon 2020, Communicating EU research and Innovation guidance for project participants, 2014.
6. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

Annex 1

List of Workshops						
Code	WP	Title	Date of Activity	Partner	Target Group	Number of people reached
W-001	WP2	Can academics be activists?	12/07/2021	UM	Academics, PhD candidates, R&I staff	25
W-002	WP2	Community-engaged research: the involvement of academic and governmental actors in climate-related flood risks	06/07/2022	UM	Academics, PhD candidates, R&I staff	29
W-003	WP4	Revise, Review, Rewrite: How to edit your academic texts as a non-native speaker	16/01/2023	UBremen	Doctoral Candidates, ECRs	14
W-004	WP4	Revise, Review, Rewrite: How to edit your academic texts as a non-native speaker	15/09/2023	UBremen	Doctoral Candidates, ECRs	7
W-005	WP4	Revise, Review, Rewrite: How to edit your academic texts as a non-native speaker	15/12/2023	UBremen	Doctoral Candidates, ECRs	12
W-006	WP4	Prioritizing and time management for PhD candidates and early career researchers with caring responsibilities	15/05/2023	Bremen + UEssex	Doctoral Candidates, ECRs	22
W-007	WP4	Prioritizing and time management for PhD candidates and early career researchers with caring responsibilities	06/12/2023	Bremen + UEssex	Doctoral Candidates, ECRs	17
W-008	WP4	Training Programme for PhD Supervisors	28/09/2023, 19/10/2023, 09/11/2023	UM	PhD supervisors	12
W-009	WP4	Proper Use of Generative AI in Research	13/01/2024, 31/01/2024	UBremen + UM	Doctoral Candidates, all researchers	20
W-010	WP2	How to run a festival: a workshop	24/04/2023	UM		11
W-011	WP2	How to start a business from scratch?	26/06/2023	UM	Young researchers, researchers who are interested to set up a company based on their research ideas.	4
W-012	WP2	Unlocking the Hidden Value: The Art of Valorization	09/07/2023	UM	Researchers and research staff	15
W-013	WP2	Circular economy: The future of sustainable living	06/11/2023	UM	Researchers and research staff	35
W-014	WP2	Community engaged research and innovation (CERI) & Participatory Research Architecture: Values and Key Principles	17/11/2023	UM	ECRs	25
W-015	WP2	Boosting community engaged research and innovation (CERI) & Participatory Research Trustworthiness	01/12/2023	UM	ECRs	28
W-016	WP2	Entrepreneurial Edge Workshop: Ignite Your Competence using the EntreComp Framework	13/12/2023	UM	Young researchers	12
W-017	WP2	Structural Adjustment for 21st Century Resilience: Transforming the Democratic Republic of Congo Economy	19/02/2024	UM	Researchers and research staff	12
Total						300

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101016967

Annex 2

YUFERING

YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH
EUROPE-WIDE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

September 2023

YUFERING highlighted in the recent DG REA Report “Progress of University Alliance Projects.”

We are happy and proud that our YUFE R&I efforts through our YUFERING project have been highlighted in a recent report of the European Commission.

The [“Progress of University Alliance Projects”](#) report, published by the European Research YUFERING logo Executive Agency (REA) of the European Commission in April 2023 highlights three Good Practices of our YUFERING project from the policy brief deliverable submitted in the summer 2022 and other project outcomes.

This report analyses the intermediate progress for the period 2021 -2022 of the 17 Alliances of European Universities funded under the “Horizon 2020 (H2020) Science with and for Society (ISA-SwIFS) Support 1-2020 Call – Support for the Research and Innovation Dimension of European Universities”.

More specifically, the input from the YUFERING policy brief and project deliverables are explicitly mentioned in the following sections of the report:

- 2.3. Tangible progress, page 17
- 3.1. Main challenges, page 20
- 5. Engaging Non-Academic Actors, 5.2. Good practices, page 29 (Flipped Knowledge Transfer (FKT))
- 5. Mainstreaming Open Science, 6.2. Good practices, page 32 (Open Science Calendar 2022)
- 6.3. Tangible progress, page 33
- 7. Citizen and Societal Engagement, 7.2. Good practices, page 36 (Community Engaged Research and Innovation (CERI) agenda setting)

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Unlocking the Hidden Value: The Art of Valorization

In today’s rapidly evolving world, academic research holds the key to unlocking a wealth of untapped potential. However, all too often, groundbreaking research remains confined within the confines of academic circles, failing to reach its full potential in terms of societal and economic impact. Enter the art of valorization – the process of transforming academic research into valuable outcomes that benefit both society and the researchers themselves.

On 7th of September 2023 Dr. Stephan Peters and Patric Machiels, active at Brightlands Campus, Netherlands, gave an online workshop on valorization of academic research.

The workshop addressed funding and commercialization, guiding researchers through the complexities of these processes. By understanding funding options and the steps required to bring research into the marketplace, participants unlocked the potential to create economic value and drive innovation.

Open Science bottom-up implementation in the YUFERING project

Open Science is indeed one of the essential elements of the “new normal” and therefore must be at the core of any research strategy. During the last two years, the YUFERING partners have been deploying a variety of actions devoted to understand the landscape of OS in their institutions and to contribute to a culture change.

From May 2022 to August 2023, a Full Open Science (FOS) pilot has been carried out to foster Open Science practices across several research teams at the universities. These have been working towards open access to publications, FAIR research data, open licenses, citizen science and open educational resources (OER), among other areas. FOS research teams are expected to become role-models and ambassadors within their institutions.

The goal of this online event that took place on 15th September 2023 was to showcase the YUFERING FOS pilot results, as well as to reserve some time to the partners to continue reflecting on how to promote OS awareness at their institutions.

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Fall highlights
Unlocking the Hidden Value: The Art of Valorization
Organizer: University of Antwerp

Open Science bottom-up implementation in the YUFERING project
Organizer: Universidad Carlos III de Madrid

Upcoming Events
[Joint SwIFS Event in Brussels](#)
November 30th and December 1st 2023

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YUFERING

YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH EUROPE-WIDE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

December 2023

Entrepreneurial Edge Workshop: Ignite your Competence using EntreComp Framework

In a world of constant change and dynamic opportunities, cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset is crucial. Join our immersive workshop on EntreComp, the European Entrepreneurship Competence Framework, providing a roadmap for individuals, teams, and organizations.

Highlights:

- Understand EntreComp's core concepts and 15 competences.
- Apply EntreComp in real-life scenarios for financial, cultural, or social value.
- Engage in interactive sessions fostering collaboration and creative thinking.
- Explore how EntreComp catalyzes personal and professional growth.
- Learn from real-world case studies across diverse fields.

Takeaways:

- Deep understanding of EntreComp.
- Practical tools for an entrepreneurial mindset.
- Strategies for applying competences in various contexts.
- Insights into shaping a future aligned with the common good.

WHEN: Wednesday, 13 December 2023
TIME: 13:00 - 15:00 CET
WHO: Honorata Falga Zuraniska (The Centre for Academic Entrepreneurship and Technology Transfer, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun)
WHERE: Online (Zoom) <https://maastrichtuniversity.zoom.us/j/8113713101737?pwd=OVk2Z2ZuXkF0QDE2Q0N0RjCSG0Ym00>
LANGUAGE: English
REGISTER HERE: <https://forms.gle/f3kxRdV1tSFYr13>

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Online Language Workshop: Revise, Review, Rewrite – How to edit your academic texts as a non-native speaker

Take your research writing the extra mile – acquire new editing skills and proofreading strategies to improve your paper's style, cohesion, clarity, and punctuation. This online workshop will provide you with input on how to better prepare your paper for publication or peer-review.

We will make use of digital materials, handouts, and exercises. The online workshop will take place in a classroom environment and include interactive group activities that will augment the trainer's input. This workshop requires **active participation and active discussions.**

In the second phase of the online workshop, you will be invited to take part in a **one-on-one consultation with the trainer (ca. 30 minutes)**. This optional consultation usually takes place in the week following the workshop and offers you the chance to look more closely at your own writing from a linguistic perspective and get suggestions on how to continue the process of becoming a better proof-reader and writer.

You are most welcome – indeed encouraged – to bring along samples of your own academic writing in English. These need not be polished excerpts or whole texts; works in progress are just as welcome, and sometimes even better suited for trying out new strategies.

WHEN: Friday, 15 December 2023
TIME: 9:00 – 16:00 CET + optional one-on-one consultation with the trainer (ca. 30 minutes) in the week following the workshop
WHO: Katrina Stollmann (Writing consultant, Language Centre Bremen)
WHERE: Online
LANGUAGE: English
SUITABLE FOR: Doctoral candidates and early career researchers (Postdoc)
SEATS: 15 (first come first served basis)
REGISTER HERE:
 Please register via the YUFE Virtual Campus
<https://virtualcampus.yufe.eu/2023/course/ig0xVNERI8SHQ24>

Registration deadline: Thursday, 7 December 2023 (23:59 CET)

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Structural Adjustment for 21st Century Resilience: Transforming the DRC Economy

Join our workshop addressing the unique economic challenges facing the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) in the 21st century. Explore tailored strategies for structural adjustments, inclusive development, and harnessing technology to fortify the DRC's economy.

Highlights:

- **21st Century Challenges:** Examine global shifts impacting the DRC and understand how to navigate these challenges.
- **Structural Adjustment Strategies:** Discuss policies and reforms to enhance economic diversification, attract investments, and boost competitiveness.
- **Inclusive Development:** Explore initiatives promoting equitable opportunities and empowerment for all.
- **Technology for Growth:** Embrace digital transformation and innovation to drive productivity and efficiency.
- **Resource Management:** Focus on sustainable use of natural resources, minimizing environmental impact.
- **Global Partnerships:** Foster international collaborations and trade partnerships for economic growth.
- **Interactive Exercises:** Engage in workshops and case studies to apply practical solutions.

Don't miss this opportunity to contribute to the transformative dialogue shaping the DRC's economic future. Join us in strategizing for resilience and growth in the 21st century.

WHEN: Wednesday, 20 December 2023
TIME: 14:00 - 16:00 CET
WHO: Cyril Luslu
WHERE: Online (Zoom)
<https://maastrichtuniversity.zoom.us/j/854367131497?pwd=VjR3ZnNmVjVjF0SjUwGk5a5a9Q0T09>
LANGUAGE: English
REGISTER HERE: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLStm81eywB_E7B428TVww5PnFzCvYy5m8B7N5c44e4WuJGcYUwformD.uspsmf_link

Winter highlights
 Entrepreneurial Edge Workshop
 Ignite your Competence using EntreComp Framework
 Structural Adjustment for 21st Century Resilience: Transforming the DRC Economy
 Organizer: University of Maastricht
 Revise, Review, Rewrite - How to edit your academic texts as a non-native speaker
 Organizer: University of Bremen

Season's Greetings from all the YUFERING team!

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YUFERING

YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH EUROPE-WIDE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

January 2024

YUFERING at the SwafS Cross - Alliance Forum 2023 R&I in European Universities Alliances

The YUFERING project was present at the SwafS Cross-Alliance Forum 2023, R&I in European Universities Alliances. The YUFE Alliance was represented by Dr. Eva M. Méndez Rodríguez (UC3M).

The event had two objectives: to share good practices and to showcase the best progress made by the Alliances in their R&I dimension. Both objectives were more than achieved.

Mapping Alliances' R&I Best Practices

The following poster highlights 32 Alliances' examples on best practices and outcomes of their R&I projects, organized around the seven transformational modules. All the Alliances' results are linked within the poster and can be accessed at once.

In addition, a contact list regarding the R&I dimension of these Alliances is also included.

Download the poster

You may download all posters presented in the event [here](#).

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Two-day Interactive Workshop: Proper Use of Generative AI in Research

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has advanced rapidly. In this process, academic research and AI have become more and more intertwined. This workshop offers an introduction to the proper use of Generative AI in research. It will take place online and include interactive activities that will augment the trainer's input.

The workshop will be structured as follows:

- Introduction to ChatGPT (or similar Large Language Model, LLM) and its capabilities.
- Hands-on session: How and when to use LLMs as a researcher.
- Examples: using diffusion models (text-to-image) in research.
- Discussion on the potential implications of generative models in research.

You will receive training material to test and deepen your learnings. In the weeks between the first and the second workshop day, you will have enough time to go through the material and apply your learnings. On the second workshop day, you will reflect on your learnings.

To maximize your learning experience, we recommend that you create a login with OpenAI (or use an existing Google account) and use ChatGPT at least once.

The workshop targets doctoral candidates and researchers who are interested in exploring the possibilities of ChatGPT in academic research.

WHO: Henry Woodruff (H.C.A.), Maastricht University

Henry is currently Assistant Professor at the Department of Precision Medicine and Head of The D-Lab. Holding a PhD in astrophysics he now employs machine learning techniques and advanced quantitative image analysis methods to bring

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precision medicine closer to clinical implementation. Currently he is working on dozens of projects focused on finding prognostic and diagnostic imaging biomarkers related to diseases such as cancer, diabetes, Alzheimer's, and stroke. Henry is a passionate educator and wishes to bring AI into the curriculum for biomedicine and medicine. He also organizes the international quantitative image analysis course AI4Imaging.

WHEN: Wednesday, 31 January 2024; 10:00 - 13:00 (CET)
Tuesday, 13 February 2024; 10:00 - 12:00 (CET)

MODE: Online

LANGUAGE: English

SEATS: 20

REGISTRATION: Please register via the YUFE Virtual Campus:
<https://virtualcampus.yufe.eu/link/course/YvNBn07QXs0IM8>

Registration start: 15 January 2024 (0:00 CET)
Registration deadline: 28 January 2024 (23:59 CET)

Winter highlights

Two-day interactive online workshop: Proper Use of Generative AI in Research
Organizer: University of Bremen

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YUFERING

YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH
EUROPE-WIDE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

February 2024

YUFERING Final Project Newsletter

The YUFERING project has reached its end, having received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and spanning a three-year period.

Aligned with the European Research Area (ERA) vision, the European Commission (EC) aims to witness crucial transformations in Research and Innovation (R&I). These changes include the encouragement of citizen science and societal engagement, the integration of Open Science practices, the promotion of knowledge circulation, the strengthening of collaboration between academia and business, and participation in a global R&I ecosystem.

The YUFE (Young Universities for the Future of Europe) alliance took on this challenge within the YUFERING project, actively contributing to piloting the necessary transformations aimed at improving and harmonizing R&I conditions in Europe.

The YUFERING project implemented actions and put forth recommendations to establish a model for an R&I system where excellence and inclusivity come together to revitalize European Universities and the R&I ecosystem. This revitalization is achieved through knowledge transfer, community engagement, and exploitation across various sectors, stakeholder groups, and countries.

Furthermore, YUFERING provided the YUFE Alliance with the opportunity to explore synergies with other European University initiatives, addressing common challenges in R&I and formulating solutions that facilitated a profound transformation of all university missions. The progress made and models developed during YUFERING offer benefits to all higher education institutions, making a tangible impact on society and economies across Europe.

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By leveraging the established collaboration among YUFE partners, YUFERING played a pivotal role as a facilitator for R&I transformation, concentrating on seven primary objectives:

- Define and implement a community-engaged R&I agenda for an outstanding and inclusive European University within the YUFE framework.
- Act as a catalyst for flipped knowledge transfer and its application in society.
- Overhaul the recognition, reward, and circulation of talents and teams across Europe.
- Establish Open Science as the standard practice by formulating a YUFE Open Science Strategy.
- Develop and strengthen shared research support structures, mechanisms, and infrastructures among YUFERING partners.
- Generate a broader impact on the R&I community and society through a horizontal focus on community-engaged R&I.
- Explore collaborative structures and exchange best practices with other European University alliances to ensure a system-level impact.

In YUFERING, the YUFE Alliance not only played a role in the essential transformation needed at various levels to enhance the R&I dimension of European Universities but also collaborated with all relevant stakeholders to create a blueprint for the future ERA.

The Project Results are available on the project's [webpage](#) as well as on [Zenodo](#).

We stand at the bittersweet moment of releasing our final project newsletter. As we reflect on this incredible journey, we are filled with gratitude for the support, engagement, and inspiration all the people we have met have brought to our project. In this final edition, we take a moment to express our heartfelt appreciation to each and every one of you who has been a part of the YUFERING project.

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